

COMPOSITIONAL CONTROLLABILITY OF THIN FILM METAL-ORGANIC MATRIX COMPOSITE MATERIALS SYNTHESIZED BY VARIABLE DUTY CYCLE PULSED PLASMA POLYMERIZATIONS

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INTRODUCTION

The use of plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PACVD) methods has long been known to provide thin films for use in a variety of applications, including synthesis of unique composite materials. The plasma technique represents an inherently attractive approach to surface modifications in that it involves a single-step, all-dry procedure which provides uniform, pin-hole free and highly conformable coatings.

In the present work, we examine the extension of the PACVD approach to films produced under variable duty cycle pulsed plasma conditions, including synthesis of metal/organic composite films. Specifically, we demonstrate large-scale progressive changes in composition of these composites with sequential variations in the pulsed plasma duty cycles employed during the deposition processes, while all other plasma variables are held constant. The film chemistry controllability is shown to be an inherent feature of the variable duty cycle pulsed plasma polymerization approach. This control is illustrated in this work using a variety of monomers, including several volatile organometallic compounds. Also, as demonstrated in this study, both the chemical compositions and the physical properties of the resultant polymeric composite films can be controlled through variations in the ratio of plasma on to plasma off times employed during the deposition process.

RESULTS

The pulsed plasma synthesized films were characterized using a variety of techniques. These included both microscopic (atomic force and scanning electron) and spectroscopic (X-ray photoelectron and Fourier transform infrared) methods. The electroactivities of these films were examined using cyclic voltammetric methods. The electrochemical properties of the plasma synthesized films were observed to be strongly dependent on the pulsed plasma duty cycles employed during film deposition of the organometallic monomer. In general, the percent metal content and the resultant electrical conductivity of these films were observed to increase as the

duty cycles employed during the polymerizations were reduced. The relatively facile controllability of the electrical conductivity of these composites represents a unique aspect of the pulsed plasma deposition approach.

The improved compositional controllability of these composite films provided by a pulsed plasma in lieu of the traditional continuous wave (CW) operational mode can be rationalized by contrasting differences in important dynamic factors operable under these two distinct deposition conditions. In particular, we observe significant increases in the film thickness per Joule of energy input under pulsed conditions relative to those obtained under CW conditions. An example of this enhanced film formation is shown in Table 1 as observed during the plasma polymerization of vinylferrocene. These results are indicative of significant film formation during the plasma off periods. We believe that film formation processes during the plasma off periods are considerably more selective than those processes occurring during plasma on periods. This increased selectivity arises primarily from the absence of ablation reactions, substrate heating, and high energy vacuum UV photons during the plasma off periods, as examined in this presentation.

Table 1: Film formation per unit energy input during pulsed plasma polymerization of vinylferrocene. All runs at 25 W peak power.

RF Duty Cycle ON/OFF (ms/ms)	Equivalent Power (Watts)	Film Thickness (Å/Joule)
10/20	0.83	80
10/50	0.42	300
10/100	0.23	350

Finally, we will describe an interesting recent extension of our pulsed plasma approach to include the coating of fibers and fine powders. For this purpose, a 360 rotatable plasma reactor has been constructed to permit uniform dispersion of these powders and fibers through the plasma discharge zones during polymerization. Thus, it is possible to provide exact compositional control of film coatings applied to powders and fibers. These film coatings can be employed to improve the bonding characteristics of these particles to the organic matrices employed in the synthesis of improved composite materials.

SUMMARY

The variable duty cycle pulsed plasma technique is shown to provide an unusually high level of compositional controllability in the synthesis of polymeric films, including metal/organic composite materials. We believe there are a wide range of potential applications for this technology, including particularly coatings for fibers and fine powders as reviewed in this presentation.